

CURRICULUM AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF EDUCATIONAL QUALITY

Mallayeva Matluba Abdumalikovna

Independent researcher

Alisher Navo'i Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and
Literature

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15321597>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th April 2025

Accepted: 29th April 2025

Online: 30th April 2025

KEYWORDS

Quality of education,
educational programs,
educational literature,
assessment, state
education standards,
technology, AI.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the stages of development, achievements and shortcomings of educational programs created in the field of literature are analyzed in a comparative way. Characteristics of the educational standard were classified and certain conclusions were drawn.

In research on teaching and learning, world scientists emphasize that the quality of education consists of four important components (composition). They are: curricula, educational literature, teaching methods and assessment. Only if these components act in harmony and in connection with each other can the quality of education produce the expected results.

The Head of State has repeatedly emphasized that the task of developing education, bringing it among the developed countries of the world, is based on the efforts being made for the development of the new Uzbekistan. Educational programs, educational literature and assessment constitute the main content of these statements. In particular, the tasks of developing the quality of education on a global scale, "improving teaching methodologies, gradually implementing the principles of individualization in the educational process; introducing modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects into the sphere of public education" were also set out in the "Concept for the Development of the Public Education System until 2030". The adoption of decrees of the Head of State aimed at improving national educational programs once again confirms its importance in developing the quality of education. For example, the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" and No. PF-134 dated May 11, 2022 "On approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022–2026" aim to bring the quality of education to a new level by creating modern curricula in all subjects, including literature.

It is known that until the 1990s of the 20th century, normative documents on literary education essentially contained Soviet ideology and the task of instilling it in young people. However, since the beginning of a new era in Uzbekistan, efforts have also been made to

reform education in all areas based on national interests and universal values. In particular, state educational standards, curricula, and literature textbooks were enriched with new approaches and principles that serve the interests of independent Uzbekistan. For example, in order to ensure the implementation of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Organization of General Secondary Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. 203 dated May 13, 1998, the Resolution on Approval of State Standards of General Secondary Education, developed by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and pilot-tested in the 1998-1999 academic years, was published. This Resolution raised the issue of the gradual introduction of state educational standards of general secondary education together with curricula in general secondary educational institutions starting from the 1999-2000 academic year. This educational standard was published in the special issue of the Bulletin of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Development of Education" for the subjects of Mother Tongue, Literature and Uzbek language (for schools where education is conducted in other languages)¹.

Any educational program is formed on the basis of the knowledge, skills and qualifications that students must acquire, as established by state educational standards. The State Educational Standard (SES) is an official pedagogical document that scientifically substantiates the minimum amount of knowledge, skills, qualifications and spiritual qualities that graduates of a certain stage of an educational institution must acquire in a specific subject (including Literature)². This document "controls", "monitors" and "draws" certain conclusions about the knowledge acquired by students in the subject of literature. The standards and curricula of literature differ from those of other subjects. For example, while knowledge, skills, or abilities are considered important in the educational standards of natural or exact sciences, in literature it is important to form the student's emotional (feeling) intelligence (concepts related to human feelings and emotions, such as feeling someone else's pain, respecting their feelings).

In addition, the knowledge, skills and qualifications that a student should acquire in the field of Literature can serve as a beacon for students throughout their lives.

The State Educational Standard adopted in 1999 includes literature as an educational subject in the aesthetic-spiritual direction. Because literature is described as an activity aimed at forming the spirituality, soul and feelings of the student. The section "Content and indicators of literary education in general secondary schools" of this State Educational Standard and Program reflects the specific characteristics of the standards and skills that a general secondary school graduate should develop in the field of literature. In particular:

- correct, fast and expressive reading of a literary text;
- feeling the state of the hero of the studied work of art and being able to convey his feelings to others to a certain extent;

¹ Ta'lim taraqqiyoti. 1- maxsus son.Umumiy o'rta ta'limning Davlat ta'lim standarti va o'quv dasturi – Toshkent.: "ShARQ" nashriyot - matbaa konserni, 1999.– 153-b.

² Ta'lim taraqqiyoti. 1- maxsus son.Umumiy o'rta ta'limning Davlat ta'lim standarti va o'quv dasturi – Toshkent.: "ShARQ" nashriyot - matbaa konserni, 1999.– 42-bet

- distinguish the most important character traits inherent in the heroes of the studied work of art;
- be able to express one's attitude to the actions and feelings of the heroes of the work of art;
- notice the most vivid artistic allusions and expressions in the studied work of art;
- notice vivid images and vivid allusions in the studied work of art and be able to express an opinion about them;
- view any work of art primarily as an aesthetic phenomenon, etc.

From the above notes, it is clear that the skills (literary indicators) that graduates of the Department of Literature should acquire cover the most important indicators specified in the subject to the greatest extent possible. For example, the student's literary theory, analysis of a work of art, understanding of subject, image, and means of expression, as well as the skills of comparing artistic and real reality, comparing the events of a work of art with events that occurred in the student's life, are very important today, and are necessary indicators for the student's life needs. However, at the same time, among these literary indicators, one can also find abstract indicators that cannot be accurately assessed. For example, in the skill of "mastering the skills of watching a stage work, listening to a song, and being able to show the sources of the charm of these types of art", there is an ambiguity in the sentence "mastering the skills of listening to a song". The student grows up familiar with music from the age of perceiving the world. He acquires the skills of listening to music on his own, understanding the essence of music, and understanding the charm and essence reflected in music. From this point of view, what exactly is meant by the above-mentioned literary skills and what this can give to the student, in our opinion, is not clarified. Or, in these literary indicators, it is also noted that the graduating student "should be able to fill out any work papers without difficulty." This literary indicator gives the impression that it serves to form not a skill specific to literature, but a skill related to another subject, for example, the mother tongue. In addition, this indicator, which is included in the literature subject, can also be included in the list of abstract, objective, and precisely assessable skills. will be. Because it is not clearly indicated what kind of worksheets are meant when it comes to worksheets, and there is uncertainty in the phrase "be able to fill in".

In the textbook "Methodology of Teaching Uzbek Literature" by scientists Z. Mirzayeva and K. Jalilov, the existing, current State Educational Standards for General Secondary Education in Literature until the creation of the National Curriculum in 2022, prepared in collaboration with UNESCO, were analyzed. The authors take a critical approach to this educational standard, emphasizing that insufficient attention is paid to the competencies inherent in the discipline of literature, and as a result, literature has lost its status as an independent discipline and has become a discipline that helps develop competencies that are formed in students in other disciplines (mother tongue, foreign language, social studies), and they try to prove their points with specific examples. In particular, the competencies named as "literary-speech competencies", such as "can retell the plot of a work of art", "can explain the depicted events and images to others", are actually competencies related to reading comprehension and speaking skills, which are developed in native language, second language and foreign language lessons, and literary concepts and methods of literary analysis do not

play any role in the development of these competencies. They make a very sharp judgment that the concept of “literary-speech competence” itself does not exist and that this concept is an artificial term invented by the authors of the standard, and they prove their opinion by citing foreign sources. Again, the authors of this textbook do not consider “literary-speech competencies” It is noted that the competence “can perform the role of heroes in small stage performances based on a work of art” included in the list is not included in the speech competence at all, but is a competence related to acting skills and plasticity. In the demonstration of stage speech and acting skills, speech, correct and effective speech, and error-free pronunciation of words and sentences are considered to be characteristic features of exemplary speech. Perhaps the teachers, methodologists, and literary critics who created the standard came to this conclusion taking into account these aspects of the competence.

Perhaps the teachers, methodologists, and literary scholars who created the standard came to this conclusion by taking into account these very aspects of competence. In general, it should be noted that the competencies established in the existing standards to date have played an important role in determining the current knowledge, skills, and qualifications of students in the field of Literature. However, changes in human thinking, aspects inherent in globalization and integration require new approaches to education. The knowledge, skills, and qualifications that students must acquire also differ from the previous ones in terms of content, essence, objectivity, and accuracy. Qozoqboy Yuldoshev also wrote the following about the new approach to pedagogy and the setting of completely new goals for education: “In many developed countries, as well as in countries where advanced pedagogical ideas have developed, a completely different goal is now being set for the science and practice of pedagogy. The focus of today's advanced pedagogy has shifted from training specialists to personality formation. That is, the focus of pedagogy is on perfecting the personality of the student in all respects, on forming him into an active person who thinks in his own way, is able to come to independent conclusions, does not try to adapt to the views of others, is creative, initiative, and is not afraid to take responsibility. ... New pedagogy deals with the formation of bright personality traits who can set themselves tasks, do not rely on someone else's words when making a decision, develop themselves, and control their own activities. The fact that knowledge alone is not enough to solve the problems of the present time, the individuals being formed in educational institutions now need to be able to look at reality with a creative eye, go beyond the limits of The importance of being able to think, in short, the formation of strong personal qualities in students is of primary importance for the new pedagogical idea”³

From this, it can be concluded that quality education and educational programs that are beneficial to the student should be based on mature educational standards in all respects. The more objective, clear, and evaluable the standards to be created in Literature, among other subjects, are based on criteria that can be evaluated, the more conceptual, systematic, and purposeful the educational programs will be formed.

³ Yo‘ldoshev Q. Jilovlanmagan tafakkur mahsuli. Toshkent: “Tafakkur” nashriyoti, 2023-yil, 27-28 betlar

References:

1. Ta'lim taraqqiyoti. 1- maxsus son. Umumiy o'rta ta'limning Davlat ta'lim standarti va o'quv dasturi – Toshkent: "ShARQ" nashriyot - matbaa konserni, 1999.– 42-bet
2. Yo'ldoshev Q. Jilovlanmagan tafakkur mahsuli. Toshkent: "Tafakkur" nashriyoti, 2023-yil, 27-28 betlar.
3. Kambarova S. Ways of organizing research activities of students in literary education // Psychology and education. 2021. 58 (2). – P. 4968–4975.
4. Kambarova S. Learning a writer's personality in the portrait genre // European Scholar Journal (ESJ). 2021. Vol. 2. – № 9. – P. 40–43. (№ 5. Global Impact Factor 7.235)
5. Kambarova S. Reality and fantasy in the oeuvre of Navoi: a combination of interpretation and analysis // American Journal of Advanced Scientific Research (AJASR). 2024. – № 4. – P. 134 – 138.
6. Kambarova S. Book, reading, education // European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA). 2024. – № 5. – P. 54–57.
7. **Ways To Use Virtual Learning Opportunities In Literature Teaching** // Eurasian Journal Of Social Sciences, Philosophy And Culture. – P. 2025. 25-fevr. – P. 50 – 56.
8. Юсуфжонова Н.Н. Туркий халқ эпосларини қиёсий-типологик ёндашув асосида ўқитиш технологияси. Пед. фан. бўй. фалс. док. (PhD) ... дисс. – Тошкент, 2022. – 144 б.